

PRINCIPLES OF SELECTION OF INFORMATION MODELING CONTENT

Siradjev Saloxiddin Negmatovich

Researcher of Karshi Engineering Economics Institute;

Tel: +998 91 213 99 29;

goldsagf@gmail.com.

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Annotation. The principles, forms and means of selecting the content of Information Modeling are presented in this article. In addition, the theoretical analysis of the pedagogical rule-principles of the professional and pedagogical direction of education is carried out.

Keywords. Modeling, information modeling, teaching methods, forms and means of teaching, professional and pedagogical orientation, pedagogical rule-principle, etc.

Introduction. Taking into account the existing models of training specialists in the field of information modeling, we will briefly list and outline the Leading Principles for choosing the content of training. On the basis of these principles, the main areas of activity in the formation of the content of education in accordance with the formed teaching concept are determined in the initial state. In our research work, six pedagogical rules-principles of the professional and pedagogical orientation of education were taken into account:

1. The principle of validity. Training a teacher in the field of Informatics should provide him with knowledge that goes beyond the school course of Informatics and ICT, and coincide with the needs of the profession to be mastered.
2. The principle of duality. The basics of building an informatics course in a pedagogical higher educational institution form a combination of general scientific and methodological lines. When working on a new material for the teacher, the overlap of the scientific and methodological aspects occurs (the teacher thinks about the change in the methodological direction in teaching at the same time when studying the new educational material).
3. The principle of a leading idea. The implementation of links between a higher education institution and school courses should be the leading idea of the course.
4. The principle of continuity. All courses studied must be involved in the process of a student's continuous understanding of the elements of pedagogical activity.
5. The principle of the use of a teacher of a pedagogical higher educational institution in pedagogical activity in new information technologies.

6. The principle of systematic use of new information technologies in education. Application of the methodology and technology of the educational and educational process using the latest electronic means of education and a computer. In education, a higher school teacher should use a computer as a means of the educational process and, moreover, widely see and understand the information picture of the world, realize his leading goal in this information environment.

- All six principles of the professional-pedagogical direction of education are associated with the methodological system of education — the systemic components of educational goals.

- Based on the above and taking into account the six principles of the professional-pedagogical direction, we will introduce and give a brief description of additional principles involved in the selection of educational content:

- the principle of taking into account the object, subject and methods of pedagogical design of Information Modeling and digital (electronic) educational resources in graphs in the complex of educational and professional tasks, which can serve as the basis for an active approach to teaching the future computer science teacher to modeling in graphs;

- the principle of structural unity of the content of the development of digital educational resources and types of information and analytical activities in the course of a computational experiment in the direction of teaching Information Modeling in graphs to solve practical problems, from general forms to private and specific forms, and ultimately in the process of education to solve it through a complex;

- the principle of compliance of the content of education with modern scientific, theoretical and practical achievements of the field of science, as well as the main stages of the activity of a specialist in the field of Information Modeling. In our opinion, the sequence of presentation of course topics should be based on the technological component and correspond to the stages of the process of creating an information model in the information system;

- the principle of accounting for the professional direction of Education. In our study, this principle, in addition to the principles of the above-mentioned professional and pedagogical orientation, is implemented through a set of educational and professional tasks, teaching to their solution forms knowledge and skills in the field of Information Modeling in graphs. As a result of education, the professional qualification of the future Informatics teacher as a specialist in

the field of Information Modeling in graphs should be formed, capable of solving tasks for the design and development of digital educational resources (RTR) using various information systems, including professional ones. Taking into account such an interpretation of this principle and with the conditions for the development of a system of educational and professional tasks in the main areas of Information Modeling and pedagogical design of the RTR in the graphs, it is possible to carry out training within the framework of a competence approach to education, which is relatively new for the Russian; stages of professional qualification the content of Education “determines the logic of” spreading”.

- the principle of practical orientation. The content of education should, first of all, ensure the achievement of such an educational goal as the creation of information models on graphs of various levels in information systems and the formation of skills for their application in the field of design and development of RTRS;
- the principle of modularity involves the presentation of educational content in the form of a modular structure, which, in turn, ensures the variativeness of the educational process;
- the principle of variativeness involves the inclusion in the content of training in Information Modeling in graphs of systems of various designations and various instrumental means of implementing information, including computer models;
- the principle of openness involves the introduction into the content of teaching new educational elements that arise in connection with the further development of information and educational technologies, in particular, Internet technologies and technologies of pedagogical design, as well as instrumental means of Information Modeling.

To determine the educational technologies that can be used in the study of information modeling, we add another: the principle of taking into account the strategy for mastering the content. Based on the analysis of the strategy for mastering the content and taking into account the content of the training of Information Modeling in graphs, it is expedient and possible to apply the first and second strategies in the process of teaching a computer science teacher to Information Modeling in graphs, that is, a strategy for gradual assimilation of content and a strategy

Conclusion / Recommendations. Thus, taking into account the listed principles of future Informatics teachers when choosing the content of training for

Information Modeling in graphs will help to improve the technical-logical training of these specialists in the field of information and analytical activities. This should motivate future Informatics teachers to form their readiness for information and analytical activities in the context of Information Modeling and the formation in the future of their information and analytical competence as part of the professional competence of a specialist.

references:

1. Chorshanbiyev, Z. E. (2019). IMPROVEMENT OF MATHEMATICAL AND SCIENTIFIC TRAINING OF ENGINEERING PERSONNEL IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. In ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ В ОБЛАСТИ ПСИХОЛОГИИ И ПЕДАГОГИКИ В УСЛОВИЯХ СОВРЕМЕННОГО ОБЩЕСТВА (pp. 241-243).
2. Чоршанбиев, З. Э. (2021). ДИФФЕРЕНЦИРОВАННОЕ ОБУЧЕНИЕ СТУДЕНТОВ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ВЫСШЕЙ МАТЕМАТИКИ В ТЕХНИЧЕСКОМ ВУЗЕ. Academy, (4 (67)), 42-47.
3. Esanpulatovich, Z. C. (2021). BASES OF USING PROJECT TECHNOLOGY IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIFFERENTIATION OF EDUCATION. Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities, 1(1.5 Pedagogical sciences).
4. Rakhimov, O. D., & Chorshanbiyev, Z. E. (2021). PROSPECTS FOR THE APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TRAINING THE "LABOR PROTECTION" COURSE. European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630), 2, 34-40.
5. Ergashev, N. (2022, May). FEATURES OF MULTI-STAGE TRAINING OF TEACHERS'CONTENT TO PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES USING CLOUD TECHNOLOGY IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITAL EDUCATION. In International Conference on Problems of Improving Education and Science (Vol. 1, No. 02).
6. Ergashev, N. (2022, May). THEORETICAL STAFF TRAINING USING CLOUD TECHNOLOGY IN CONTINUING EDUCATION. In International Conference on Problems of Improving Education and Science (Vol. 1, No. 02).
7. Ergashev, N. (2022, May). PROBLEMS OF USING DIGITAL EDUCATION IN PEDAGOGICAL THEORY AND PRACTICE. In International Conference on Problems of Improving Education and Science (Vol. 1, No. 02).
8. Ergashev, N. (2022, May). THEORY OF TRAINING OF PEDAGOGICAL PERSONNEL IN HIGHER EDUCATION USING CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITAL EDUCATION. In International Conference on Problems of Improving Education and Science (Vol. 1, No. 02).
9. Ergashev, N. (2022, May). PROBLEMS OF DIGITAL EDUCATION IN PEDAGOGICAL THEORY AND PRACTICE. In International Conference on Problems of Improving Education and Science (Vol. 1, No. 02).

10. G'ayratovich, E. N. (2022). The Theory of the Use of Cloud Technologies in the Implementation of Hierarchical Preparation of Engineers. Eurasian Research Bulletin, 7, 18-21.
11. Ergashev, N. (2022). UZLUKSIZ TA'LIM SHAROITIDA MUXANDISLAR MALAKASINI OSHIRISHNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING METODIK SHARTLARI. Journal of Integrated Education and Research, 1(2), 54-59.
12. Ergashev, N. (2022). BULUTLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR SHAROITIDA MUXANDISLARNI KASBIY FAOLIYATGA TAYYORLASH MUAMMOSINING AMALDAGI HOLATI. Journal of Integrated Education and Research, 1(2), 49-53.
13. G'ayratovich, E. N. (2022). The Problem of Training Future Engineer Personnel on the Basis of Cloud Technology in Technical Specialties of Higher Education. Eurasian Scientific Herald, 13, 1-4.

